

How Does Corporal Punishment Influence Behavioral Outcomes In Adolescents?

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ABSTRACT

Corporal punishment is a form of discipline that has been defined as bodily punishment of any kind. In fact, as of 2021 according to the World Health Organization, around 60% of children globally aged 2–14 years regularly suffer physical punishment by their parents or other caregivers, with spanking being one of its most common forms. Studying corporal punishment is crucial as it has the potential to help improve parenting practices and ensure that people are aware of the negative effects of enforcing corporal punishment on children. One of the many potential negative effects of corporal punishment during childhood and adolescence is poor behavioral outcomes in adolescence, however, more research is needed on this topic as not much research looks at this during the adolescent stage of life. This paper explores how corporal punishment may influence adolescent behavioral outcomes. More specifically, the main focus of this research is the links between corporal punishment and adolescent aggressive and antisocial behavior. This study hypothesizes that children exposed to corporal punishment tend to develop increased aggression and antisocial behavior as they grow. A potential implication of this research is recommendations for better parental practices, and drawing light on this issue could lead to more mental health services for kids as they grow up.

Keywords: corporal punishment, adolescence, aggression, antisocial behavior, interventions, cross-cultural

1. INTRODUCTION

Corporal punishment is defined as using physical force toward a child to control their behavior, intended to cause some degree of pain or discomfort (Rimal & Pokharel, 2013). There are several methods of corporal punishment, including hitting, slapping, spanking, shaking, punching, kicking, choking, electric shock, confinement in small spaces, excessive exercise, and fixed postures for extended periods (Grayson, 2006). Historically, corporal

punishment has been considered acceptable in cultures around the world, such as in many countries in Asia and Africa. However, many countries are slowly abolishing corporal punishment, and according to UNICEF, about 65 countries have banned corporal punishment as of 2023. This is a vast improvement from 1958 when Sweden was the only country that had banned corporal punishment. However, there is still a long way to go, and corporal punishment is still a pressing problem that affects children and adolescents around the world. As of 2017, corporal punishment has been banned from public schools in only 31 of 50 states in the United States (Global Initiative, 2016).

While there has been research on corporal punishment and its adverse effects on kids, there is minimal research done on corporal punishment and its effects on adolescents (age 10 to 19); therefore, more research is needed on the developmental impacts of corporal punishment on adolescents and the best methods to intervene with parents who use corporal punishment. The purpose of this literature review is to explore the behavioral and psychological impacts of corporal punishment on children and adolescents, examining how it influences their aggression, social skills, and long-term development. Additionally, this review aims to explore cultural variations in attitudes towards corporal punishment, shedding light on how social norms and traditions shape its acceptance or rejection in different communities. Finally, it investigates potential interventions and strategies to mitigate the use of corporal punishment such as educational programs, to promote alternate disciplinary methods that are both effective and supportive of healthy child development. In examining existing research in these areas, this paper aims to bring awareness to the immense impact of corporal punishment and highlight ways to mitigate it to protect children's mental and emotional well-being.

2. DISCUSSION

2.1 How corporal punishment can influence Adolescent behavior

Corporal punishment has been shown to have many negative effects on young people. Some of these negative effects include poor academic performance, antisocial tendencies, and major aggressive behaviors.

For example, in a previous research study conducted at a university in Pakistan on kids ages 14-16 years old, the researchers hypothesized that corporal punishment corrects negative behavior. However, the study revealed that corporal punishment had detrimental effects on students' behavior and academic performance (Arif & Rafi, 2007). In contrast, psychological

treatments (i.e., when the teacher talked with the students about their behavior) were more effective in improving students' behavior and learning outcomes. It is important to note that this research was conducted in Pakistan, where corporal punishment has historically been an accepted practice. Additionally, while the study investigates the effects of corporal punishment on students' behavior and academic performance, there are ethical concerns regarding the methodology, as it subjects one group of children to corporal punishment.

Furthermore, corporal punishment has been associated with the development of antisocial tendencies in children. Antisocial tendencies are defined as a pattern of behavior that may include aggression, criminal activity, or something that breaks social norms or infringes on the rights of others (American Psychological Association, 2013). Since corporal punishment often brings about feelings of shame and guilt, these emotions can drive children to withdraw socially, reinforcing their antisocial behavior. For example, a research study by Gámez-Guadix et al. (2010) conducted in the Community of Madrid involved 1,071 university students who lived with two parents or stepparents at age ten. It was found that corporal punishment in childhood was associated with higher levels of antisocial traits in young adulthood. In this study, corporal punishment was defined as the use of physical force with the intention of causing a child to experience pain, but not injury, for purposes of correction or control of the child's behavior (Straus, 2001). Notably, this occurred even when there was positive parenting present in the household, highlighting the long-term negative impacts of such discipline (Gámez-Guadix et al., 2010).

Lastly, a research study by Neaverson et al. (2020) examined the connection between self-control and exposure to corporal punishment in predicting aggression over time in adolescents. This longitudinal study followed 1,360 children from the age of 7 until 20. This study hypothesized that high self-control would protect adolescents from the negative effects of corporal punishment, reducing the likelihood of developing aggressive behaviors. The results indicated an association between higher self-control and lower levels of aggression in adolescents. Still, self-control did not consistently moderate the relationship between corporal punishment and aggression, indicating that aggression is one of the detrimental consequences of corporal punishment, even when controlling for individual differences among children. Exposure to corporal punishment has often been associated with increased aggression in adolescents and children, meaning that corporal punishment might serve as a prime example

of observational learning. This form of learning can significantly shape how young individuals perceive and respond to their environment.

As demonstrated by previous studies, poor academic performance, aggression, and antisocial behaviors can be seen in children and adolescents when they experience corporal punishment. These findings suggest that corporal punishment has long-term effects and it can often affect how a child or adolescent thinks and perceives things around them.

2.2 Corporal Punishment Across Cultures

Corporal punishment varies widely in acceptance and implementation across different cultures. While some societies view it as a traditional and necessary means of instilling discipline, others consider it outdated and harmful. While some societies view corporal punishment as a way of instilling discipline, others consider it outdated and harmful. For example, in countries like Pakistan and some regions of Africa, corporal punishment remains culturally accepted and is often used as a tool for instilling discipline. In contrast, nations like Sweden and New Zealand have banned corporal punishment in all settings.

For example, in a literature review conducted by Lansford (2010) on culture and corporal punishment, it was found that the effects of corporal punishment on children's behavior varied by cultural context. In cultures where corporal punishment is common, children may view it as normal, reducing its negative impact. On the other hand, in cultures where it is rare, children may perceive it as hostile, leading to more behavioral problems. In a 2010 review, it was noted that African American families in the U.S. employed corporal punishment more frequently than European American families. Additionally, the study found that frequent use of corporal punishment is linked to higher aggression and anxiety in children in multiple countries, especially in places where such punishment is less typical.

Furthermore, a research study conducted by Flynn (1998) examined how views on corporal punishment differ by race, age, and type of misbehavior. Perceptions on whether spanking was appropriate varied depending on the gender and race of the participant as well as the context of the corporal punishment (e.g., the behavior it was punishing). This study showed that men and African American individuals tend to support spanking more than women and White individuals in the US. Spanking was also considered more suitable for younger children and serious misbehaviors. This study showed that, at least in 1998, attitudes about

spanking varied substantially between individuals. Understanding these cultural perspectives is crucial for understanding the broader implications of corporal punishment on child development and education in diverse societies.

2.3 Interventions to Combat Corporal Punishment

Corporal punishment is prevalent around the world, and one way to overcome it is through interventions. Interventions can help caregivers, parents, and teachers understand the negative impact of corporal punishment and learn non-harmful methods of disciplining children. By educating them on more effective and humane approaches, we can reduce the use of physical punishment and promote healthier relationships with children.

A research study conducted by Hornor et al. (2015) focused on interventions for corporal punishment; they examined how a one-hour educational session changed people's views on spanking children. The session covered what discipline is, the harms of spanking, efforts to stop it in various countries, and better ways to discipline children. The sessions were conducted either in schools or online. The intervention resulted in decreased support for spanking. Additionally, those who had never been spanked as children were the most opposed to spanking. Overall, the session effectively encouraged people to use non-physical methods of discipline.

Additionally, Gershoff (2017) examined interventions to reduce corporal punishment in schools. One notable intervention is the Good Schools Toolkit in Uganda, which trained teachers in non-violent discipline and significantly reduced instances of corporal punishment by 42%. Another intervention done by this research group was ActionAid's Stop Violence Against Girls in School initiative, which used advocacy and education in Ghana, Kenya, and Mozambique to decrease physical punishment, especially for girls.

These studies provide examples of alternative disciplinary methods to corporal punishment. Bringing awareness of these alternative methods to parents and educators can positively influence adolescent development. In addition to direct interventions for corporal punishment, researchers have also studied effective disciplinary methods that are not harmful to children's development. Some of these methods are positive reinforcement, setting clear expectations, and having logical consequences for actions. These positive discipline methods

can help children learn from their mistakes while avoiding the negative psychological impacts and fear associated with corporal punishment.

3. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, corporal punishment remains a global issue affecting children and adolescents. The hypothesis that children exposed to corporal punishment would have higher tendencies to be more aggressive and antisocial as they grow up was partially supported. Studies found that when kids are exposed to corporal punishment they are more likely to be antisocial and have higher aggressive tendencies towards others as they grow up. Furthermore, more research is needed to identify effective interventions for corporal punishment. This is crucial as better intervention techniques could help parents and teachers understand the negative effects of corporal punishment, which in turn can help children and adolescents.

4. LIMITATIONS

While this review partially supported the main hypothesis, it also highlighted several limitations in the existing literature. Most of the studies were correlational due to ethical constraints, making it challenging to establish causality. Additionally, much of the research focused on children, with limited studies specifically targeting adolescents.

The scarcity of research on corporal punishment's effects during adolescence is particularly concerning. Adolescents undergo significant developmental changes and experience complex emotions, making them especially vulnerable to negative impacts. Therefore, further research is needed to better understand how corporal punishment affects adolescents during this critical developmental period.

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